

Let's play equal! Researching mechanisms of inequalities in the music and games sectors using the Global Production Network approach

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ABSTRACT

This paper researches the mechanisms generating inequalities in the music and games sectors using the Global Production Network approach. It explores where, how and in what form inequalities are found in the music and games sectors through the examination of three case studies. By unpacking the structure and dynamics of the production network of each case study, it identifies power imbalances and how inequalities are created through different power relations. Three types of inequalities are discussed, namely market access, gender and inter-sectional, and working conditions. The paper also showcases the importance of the GPN perspective for the CCS: GPN enables a holistic understanding of inequalities in different phases of CCS in a detailed and causal way which can, in turn, facilitate the adoption of policies and measures that address all phases of the production network rather than concentrating in just one.

1. Introduction

During the past few years, developments in technology and digitalisation have led to manifold changes in the cultural and creative sectors (CCS) (Benghozi & Paris, 2016; Bürkner & Lange, 2017). Because of their relationship with, and dependence on, technology and digitalisation, music and games are those CCS very much impacted, and at different levels, by these developments (KEA 2022): in the music sector, formats and distribution changes have led to reconfiguration of networks, with new actors arising and shaping the sector, but also with regulation to be left way behind (Henriksson & Janowska, 2023). Games have become more complex, have spread through more platforms, and competition in the sector has increased (Tomova et al., 2023). These developments have not only brought forward positive changes in both sectors but have also had negative implications such as creating or augmenting asymmetries and inequalities.

Our paper concentrates on the latter, but it does not seek to just examine inequalities pertaining to the music and the games sectors-

these have been extensively discussed in CCS literature already. Our aim is to contribute to this discussion by highlighting the mechanisms that create these inequalities, and starting from there see how, within the networks of these two sectors which are dominated by global actors, these inequalities emerge and are maintained. We are interested, therefore, not only in the inequalities themselves, but also how and where they occur, and which actors are involved in this process.

To be able to identify these *how*, *who* and *where* as well as their interconnections, we deploy the global production network (GPN) approach. Inequalities are interlinked with power relations and value, and the use of GPN allows us to investigate both: we look into power relations to see where and how imbalances occur, and we research where value is created and who captures it, in order to identify where in a production network inequalities are located, and how and by whom they are created. In that sense, we also contribute to the wider CCS scholarship by presenting an analytical framework that can be used to highlight different layers and perspectives of complex issues the CCS are facing, and which can serve in improving policy making.

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After the literature review below, we discuss the contribution of the GPN to the understanding of inequalities in the CCS and then present a detailed methodology including our rationale for the case studies selection. We then analyse the power concentration for each of our case studies and the three different categories of inequalities identified, namely market access, gender and intersectionality, and working conditions, followed by the conclusions.

2. Literature review

2.1. Inequalities in the cultural and creative sectors

Although there is a common perception that CCS promote accessibility, equality and tolerance (Haisch & Klöpper, 2014), evidence suggests otherwise. Inequalities are not new to the CCS and have been discussed from different perspectives (see for example van der Hoeven & Hitters, 2023; Cote and Harris, 2023; IGDA, 2021; Raine & Strong, 2019; UNESCO, 2019; d'Ovidio, 2015). Inequalities can also be observed in a series of different dimensions; the ones we focus on in this paper are those that act as barriers hindering diversity in work practices and social representations.

The music sector is characterised by an oligonomy, where major recording companies act as buyers in their interactions with artists (oligopsony), while individual consumers make up a large group of buyers on the other side (oligopoly) (Janowska, 2024; Kloosterman et al., 2019b) and is dominated by global corporations where economic value dictates success, overshadowing the impact of reputation and merit. Sony, Warner and Universal are the three major labels who together make up the majority of the recording industry in Europe and globally (European Commission, 2017 in Kloosterman et al., 2019a, p. 41).

Employment in the sector has a strong project-based nature (Watson, 2012), with the term "gig economy" (now also prevalent in the digital economy labour system) describing short-term, fast-paced work projects originating from the music industry (Haynes & Marshall, 2018). This structure brings inherent risks of income gaps and a lack of social security. The move towards more project-based work has also led to negative changes in employment and job security, precarious working conditions and exhausting work regimes (Watson, 2013, p. 2). Poor labour market conditions, atypical labour and project-based work is also common in the games sector, with professionals being prone to health issues by the lack of movement from sitting on a desk for most of the day, or burnouts (Tomova et al., 2023). The term "crunch," denoting extended periods of overtime needed to complete a game, prevails in the games sector and can result in health issues, mental health implications, family problems, and a pervasive overtime culture (Tomova et al., 2023; Cote and Harris, 2023).

Precarious labour and challenging working conditions in the CCS also coexist with gender-related inequalities (Sharp, 2021; Cote and Harris, 2023). In the music sector these include marginalisation (Raine & Strong, 2019), limited access to networks (Leonard, 2017), lower presence on playlists (Lafrance et al., 2011; Werner, 2020) and fewer leadership roles (Dodd, 2012). A 2021 report reveals the male dominance in pop music with approximately 21% of female artists in the US Billboard Hot 100 Year-End Chart, around 12% songwriters, and less than 3% music producers (Smith et al., 2021). In the US jazz domain only 10% of students are women and gender disparities persist with

women (McAndrew and Widdop, 2021; Van Vleet, 2021).

In the gaming industry, females are severely underrepresented (Women in Games, 2023).¹ In 2022, only 20% of worldwide professionals were women, despite women constituting approximately half of all players globally (GDC, 2022; Women in Games, 2023). According to the 2021 survey of the International Game Developers Association (IGDA), "the prototypical game industry worker is a White man in his early thirties with a university degree who lives in North America and does not have children" (IGDA, 2021, p. 10), with three quarters of participants to be identified as Caucasian/White/European and most to come from the USA and Canada (46%) and Europe (34%). 74% of participants believed there was no equality, with many experiencing or witnessing various forms of inequity including microaggressions, unfair salary, working hours, hiring or promotions (IGDA, 2021, p. 18–19).

2.2. The contribution of the global production network approach to understanding inequalities in the CCS

Most studies on inequalities in the CCS focus on specific professional categories (Farrugia, 2012) but the mechanisms that create these inequalities have not received equal attention. To redress this, we utilise the Global Production Network (GPN) perspective, inspired by Coe and Yeung (2015) and operationalized following Kloosterman et al. (2019b). A central element in the GPN approach is a production network which consists of five key phases, namely production, creation, distribution, exchange, and archiving (Kloosterman et al., 2019b, p. 34). The GPN approach unravels activities and actors across them but also enables the examination of power structures within the whole network (Coe and Yeung, 2015).

Coe and Yeung (2015) emphasise that in a competitive environment, individual actors, both economic and non-economic, develop strategies that lead to the formation of specific production network configurations with different spatial and relational power dynamics. For instance, financial resources and marketing capabilities are often concentrated among a few dominant actors who can potentially marginalise smaller, local players. This perspective not only illuminates the exploitation of local networks by more powerful global players but also underscores the importance of considering spatial and relational dimensions of power in the study of creative industries.

The GPN perspective also highlights the geographical dimension of production chains. With the globalisation of financing and marketing in the creative economy, this perspective becomes particularly insightful (Wu, 2017). Its global viewpoint is crucial as it highlights how global production networks transcend local boundaries, creating complex interdependencies and power dynamics that can either benefit or disadvantage local ecosystems. It also enables us not only to explore spatially diverse networks, but also research the whole network (Kloosterman et al., 2019a). This holistic view is particularly important for the music and games sectors, which are both spatially dispersed and increasingly globalised.

The GPN approach can analyse complex systems structured in different phases and highlight key activities and interrelations from the concept of a product to its consumption and archiving (Vriesema et al., 2024). By examining the entire production network, the GPN approach captures inequalities in different parts of the network rather than focusing narrowly on one aspect such as creation or exchange. For example, it allows us to see how creative ideas generated in one place

¹ The full report "state of the industry 2022" is available here <https://reg.gdconf.com/state-of-game-industry-2022>.

can be seized and commercialised by more powerful actors in another one, leading to a concentration of economic benefits away from the original creators.

Most importantly for our case, the GPN provides a comprehensive tool to analyse the complex and often unequal power relations in the CCS. By examining how power is distributed and exercised across different phases and locations within the production network, we can better understand the broader implications for local creative ecosystems. Understood as relational, power is central in this approach, encompassing elements such as finance, skills, and contacts (Lorenzen, 2018).

Through identifying power imbalances, the GPN framework can therefore shed light on inequalities related to access to and position in the market, gender, and working conditions. Gender disparities for example are widespread in the creative industries (Alacovska & O'Brien, 2021), with women often underrepresented in leadership roles and certain technical fields within the music and games sectors. This underrepresentation is not just a result of personal choices but is also influenced by systemic biases and barriers within these global networks that a GPN approach can help highlight.

Working conditions within the creative industries can also vary significantly, with precarious employment and exploitation being common (Comunian and England, 2020). Freelancers and gig workers, who constitute a large portion of the workforce in the music and games sectors, often lack job security, benefits, and fair compensation (Deresiewicz, 2020). The GPN approach here can highlight disparities in working conditions by examining how labour practices differ across various nodes of the production network and how power imbalances contribute to inequitable working conditions.

Access to and position in the market is another area where inequalities can occur. Smaller and local players often struggle to compete with larger, more established entities that have greater financial resources, market reach, and brand recognition. This disparity is exacerbated by the global nature of the production networks, where local talents can be overshadowed by international competitors with more substantial backing. The GPN perspective allows us to understand how these market dynamics operate across different geographical scales and how they impact the ability of local actors to thrive.

3. Methodology

The empirical research for this paper is part of CICERONE,² a large-scale research project in the framework of Horizon2020 applying the Global Production Network on the cultural and creative sectors. As the project research was qualitative in nature, empirical data was gathered through interviews using a common interview guide. Interviews were conducted both online and in person.

During the project research we identified common characteristics between the music and the games sectors which include governance (namely the structure of power distribution, which we have shown in figures in the next section), and the impact of digitalisation as it interplays with the development of digital products and globalisation in both industries. The variables we analysed were the structure of the GPN and the mechanisms that generate inequalities. We identified that all different categories of inequalities actually are the effects and consequences of power relations and imbalances. In that sense, in both music and games there is a big gap between major actors who dominate the market and independent ones which struggle to enter and remain; also, both sectors comprise many different actors that are globally dispersed.

The GPN approach uses the network as its analytical tool (Kloosterman et al., 2019a, p. 4). Our three case studies are therefore the respective production networks in the music and games sectors. The choice of interviewees was dictated by the use of the GPN approach, which enabled us to select interviewees from different phases of the production network. Although our main entry points were in Austria, Sweden and Poland, interviews were also conducted with actors outside these countries. All case studies primarily focus on independent and locally embedded actors, but there were also international actors involved mainly in the production and distribution phases such as major labels, publishers and online distribution platforms. We conducted 41 interviews in total, 13 for each of the two music sector production networks and 15 for the games.

The music sector networks focused on independent actors and looked at two different categories, one profit driven and one merit driven, to capture different perspectives. One of the cases is a production network in Stockholm surrounding a debuting independent artist, and the other focuses on an established jazz band, an independent niche genre with its own network structure based in Warsaw and extending to Germany. Sweden is one of the few countries that exports more music than it imports and is the third largest exporter of music globally. Many global artists and producers start there, and as such it is interesting to see how a debuting artist taps into this existing ecosystem as their production network is assembled (Power, 2003; Power & Jansson, 2004). The Polish school of jazz was known as early as the 1950s (Polski jazz, nd), researching, therefore, a music genre with such a long tradition was interesting regarding the types of inequalities that could be detected. The case study on the games sector focused on different actors located in and around Vienna, their interrelations and how their network is situated on a global level. We chose Vienna because although its gaming sector is small, it hosts highly specialised actors in the field, with developed networks and interactions with international players. Undertaking research in three different European countries allowed us not only to identify different types of inequalities in the music and games sectors and analyse the conditions that affect them, but also see if there are any shared similarities across Europe.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Identifying power relations in the games and music sectors using the GPN approach

We have used figures to show actors (creators, customers, suppliers, intermediaries, consumers, distributors and civil society) within the production network of the case studies and locate them according to the power concentration in the five different production phases. The more centralised the power within a certain phase, the closer the actors are to the centre of the circle; the more dispersed the power, the further away they are from the centre.

Two networks, one in Sweden and one in Poland, were studied for the music sector. Both belong to the independent music industry, have a similar space in the landscape but represent two different networks: the first (Sweden) unpacks the network of a debuting folkpop artist, whereas the second (Poland) focuses on the network of an established jazz trio.

The Sweden case (see Fig. 1) discusses the production network of a female debuting artist who recorded her music with a well-established producer she knew through contacts. Together they created a record label and were the sole actors in the creation and production phase, writing and producing the recorded album. Through owning the master

² See <https://cicerone-project.eu/>.

1) Musician & studio owner, 2) Direct customers (music streaming, live shows), external record company, 3) External record company, PR-agency, live manager, venue bookers, collection society & publisher 4) Social media, distributors, radio, studio owner, 5) Customers, 6) External record company

Fig. 1. Power concentration of the Swedish debuting artist network.

recordings and registering the written songs at a collection agency, they controlled the entirety of the products and activities of these two phases, concentrating a lot of power within them. They formed a core project team to aid in the distribution phase of the album, contracting a PR-agency, a live management agency and signing distribution rights to an external independent record label. The exchange phase, where the end product reaches customers, was mainly mediated through global streaming platforms and live shows. Around this core team were a number of other actors - such as concert bookers, digital platforms, other artists, a music publisher – that together make up the production network. Apart from the artist, the main actors of the project team were all well-established in the independent music industry of Stockholm with dispersed concentration of power between them.

The Polish case (see Fig. 2) features a well-established jazz Trio collaborating with a globally recognized independent jazz label. Throughout the value chain in recording, concerts, and music publishing, the Trio works with various actors whose power varies by stage. The highest power concentration is in the creation phase, where the band makes music.

The recording company oversees the production phase, transforming ideas into marketable products and significantly influencing the creative outcome. In live music, this phase involves concert agencies, festival organisers, booking agents, venues, the band’s manager, and musicians, with power varying by industry position. Large concert halls set high

entry barriers, but jazz concerts are typically held in smaller venues, resulting in more dispersed power.

The distribution of recorded music, both physical and digital, is managed globally by Universal Music, a major player acting as a gate-keeper. Likewise, music publishing companies handle placing music in derivative products and managing copyrights, concentrating power due to the oligopolistic market nature.

The exchange phase occurs when consumers engage with the music. Online, power is concentrated among a few leading streaming platforms like Spotify and Apple Music, while in concerts, power is more dispersed among venues and the band. The Trio’s reputation and association with a reputable label make them highly sought after by various venues, proving their power in the value chain.

The Trio’s network includes both independent entities and market-controlling players. Analysis of power across the five phases shows concentration in production and distribution, aligning with previous music sector studies (Curien and Moreau, 2010; Janowska, 2024; Tschmuck, 2014; Wikström, 2020).

For the games sector, we focused on production networks of three different games companies with different sizes: a Viennese startup, a small-medium (SME) sized independent studio in Vienna and a major international publisher, all somehow connected to each other: The SME knew about the startup, supported the young developers, and cooperated with the major publisher in the distribution phase. The startup

1) creators (musicians/ record label) 2) customer (manager) 3) specialised or generic suppliers (recording studio)/ concert agencies/ booking agents/ venues) 4) intermediaries (global distribution company/ online intermediaries/ media) 5) consumers (music listeners/ collectors) 6) distributors (music publishing company/ streaming platforms/ brick-and-mortar) 7) civil society (collecting societies, festival organisers - public/ museums) 8) state (state agencies promoting music)

Fig. 2. Power concentration in the Polish Jazz Trio network.

consists of four young women who just started developing their own original games. This is an atypical case given the low number of women in the sector, but it enabled us to identify commonalities such as the difficulty of women especially of young age, to access the sector, as well as divergences such as the type of games created - more emotional and with more female characters. The SME focuses on producing their own games but also in delivering specialised services to other, often bigger, companies, who outsource special activities.

The actors here are divided among the production phases: studios, designers and developers in the creation phase; studios, strategic partners and developers in the production phase; publishers, majors and marketing companies in the distribution phase; gamers, influencers and events in the exchange phase and other organisations from companies to museums in the archiving phase. Activities include designing, planning and organising a game (creation); developing, artistic production and programming (production); playing and festivals (exchange); and archiving. For each of the activities there are networks and associations within each phase. Power relations are dispersed and concentrated to the specific actors in the creation and production phase, whereas in the distribution phase they are concentrated as a result of the gatekeepers who are strongly present in that phase. Power relations become dispersed in the exchange phase and concentrated again in the archiving phase. The spatial focus is local in the creation, production and archiving phases (although in the production phase it can be global as well), and global in the distribution and exchange phases.

Fig. 3 shows the power concentration of the games case study. The

highest concentration of power and the highest concentration of actors takes place in the production and the distribution phase. Looking at the power relations in the five different production phases, it appears that the distribution phase has the highest concentration in gatekeepers.

4.2. Market access

In the music sector, although artists are central, the recording label stands out as the most influential entity in the network in both our cases. In the Polish case this is especially clear, as its dominance is symbolic, rooted in its renowned status in jazz music production, built upon the founder's charisma. Operating as a gatekeeper, the label sets high entry barriers, selecting only musicians showcasing originality, innovation, and high-performance levels in jazz.

Moreover, the label influences artistic direction, shaping projects to align with its music image, which extends beyond production to the creative phase: 'it's not that he [the producer] orders us to do something, but thanks to his experience, knowledge, and long-term co-operation with numerous other artists, he has a good overview [...] and intuition, which leads us [...] in the studio' (Trio leader). As an independent company, the label partners with a major distributor to effectively promote and distribute records globally. The power relationship is balanced, with the label focusing on high-quality products and the major's global distribution channels expanding international reach.

In the Swedish network, independent actors working with producing and distributing music are hesitant when adding new artists to their

1) Creators/label/brand: Studios, Artists 2) Customer: Diverse: either major publishers or end consumers; 3) Supplier generic: e.g. equipment for producing games; 3) Suppliers specialised: Composers for music games, IT experts, designer, programmers; 4) Intermediaries: Media, Influencers, Distribution Platforms; 5) Consumers: Gamers, Pro-Gamers; 6) Distributors: Publishers, online platforms, logistics & retailers; 7) Civil Society: communities of actors, associations, museums, festivals, events; 8) State – multilevel: Schools & university programmes, funding agencies

Fig. 3. Power concentration in the Viennese games network.

repertoire, often looking for artists that have established themselves before collaborating with them. The debuting artist had the opportunity to meet several record labels, PR-agents and other actors before the final team was assembled, even though the album had not yet been produced.

While major record labels have the capacity to do many things in-house, or bring in external companies, the independent music sector is more of a mosaic structure where a number of actors are brought together for a project and then disbanded. For independent actors in the production and distribution phase this means having to turn down most requests from artists - not because of the poor quality or potential of the music, but because they lack appropriate staff. Artists under a reputable label gain also increased access to prestigious international festivals, leveraging the label's strong brand reputation. This influence also fosters collaborations with renowned concert agencies and esteemed venues, providing a notable advantage in the concert scene.

In music publishing, signing with a global company offers writers and composers advantageous opportunities. While local artists contract with the local branch, global affiliation enhances prospects for both local and international recognition. However, established artists have a more advantageous position compared to newcomers facing higher risks and less favourable terms.

Collaboration with a recognized label ensures quality assurance, elevating the artist's brand and enhancing project value. The label's extensive network strengthens the artists' negotiation power. Yet, institutional actors, e.g. streaming platforms that often inadequately compensate creators, benefit the most in value capture. Additionally, the label and distributor also capture a significant portion of the value, while the publishing company reaps rewards from the increased product/project value.

The games sector is a global market as games are usually produced to

be distributed all over the world. Furthermore, the production process includes actors from all over the globe. Accessing the market therefore means building international networks, gaining international experience and reputation. The Viennese games sector is not as present in the global arena as the sectors in other European capitals such as Barcelona or Warsaw where there are more major firms, educational institutions and public awareness for the sector. Actors in the games sector are usually highly specialised and have years of work experience and education in the sector. Education, skills and professional experience acquisition as well as the development of international networks outside Austria are crucial factors for market access.

Networks are also crucial here as firms need to rely on international publishers and marketing platforms to reach global audiences. National initiatives such as funding schemes, networking events, and branches of major subsidiary companies support the development of better market access for local start-ups. Our fieldwork has disclosed various examples of local and international initiatives that help making the market more accessible and support international networking: Festivals such as the Vienna Gamecity in the city hall, the CIVA festival, a subversive media art festival, the gamescom in Cologne, raise awareness to local actors and connect international actors with each other.

Market access in the games sector includes the relationship to big international gatekeepers such as Ubisoft, Nintendo or Sony as they are crucial in the distribution phase. There are many independent SMEs or highly specialised self-entrepreneurs that have successfully accessed the market and cooperate with majors. Strategies to support the relationship between majors and local SMEs and raise awareness for new talents include networking events, conferences, exhibitions and fairs.

Producing music and games is a high financial and investment risk, which in the case of games is much longer and more expensive.

Interviews in both sectors highlighted how artists need to establish a network or get a contract with an established company before beginning to build up a proper network to disseminate their work. This often translates into having already built value in the form of an artistic brand or following before being able to get signed.

The findings above have a distinct market-driven nature marked by high entry barriers favouring a select few, limiting opportunities for new artists. Even established artists remain reliant on powerful gatekeepers, who not only control access but also claim the majority of the value generated, adhering to the principle of ‘the winner takes all’. Gatekeepers are connected with inequalities related to reputation, trust, long-term relationships and structural conditions of the sector such as the size of companies, and as such they are drivers of inequalities. The role of gatekeepers is to choose artists with high chances of success and reject those who may not fit into a certain market because their products lack quality, but also because they don’t have points of contact with the right gatekeepers.

Our findings make clear that inequalities in the music sector arise throughout the network as power is concentrated at gatekeepers across every phase. Gatekeepers contribute to the creation or sustenance of inequalities, appear in most production phases but concentrate most in the production and distribution phase, when big publishers and labels select certain products, services or partners and reject others. Although the digital nature of music and gaming products means that the barriers to creating and producing them are low, our research shows that without access to gatekeepers within the local-regional ecosystem these products are less likely to attract attention. Building rapport and trust with gatekeepers is therefore key; access to them can take years to develop, with negative implications for the careers of creatives in the meantime.

4.3. Gender and intersectionality

We identified a considerable lack of female actors in every phase of the GPN in all case studies, which is another starting point for comparison. One of our interview partners from the games sector referred to intersectionality issues: “gamers are almost like a joke at this point. The gaming industry is, I mean, not the industry, but the gamers can be pretty racist.” Discrimination can also be found at the creation and production phase:

“Personally, we also experienced a fair share of sexism ... Our game only had female characters, mostly because our artist prefers drawing female characters. But people thought we were pushing a political agenda. And we had to hear a lot of stupid stuff from our male colleagues at school who actually accused us of sexism - which is quite ridiculous, because consider how many games there are without any female characters. (...) since we’re women in a male dominated field, people will just assume it is political” (young female startup member)

The SME we researched tries to increase internal diversity and sensitise their employees towards fair language use. And although only 10% of its employees are female, since there is a lack of developers in general and a bigger shortage in female workforce, the company struggles to hire more female developers.

Stereotypes also determine the educational path of young trainees: “there is a lot of potential that gets lost (...) we need to break clichés”. The SME also developed games with strong female and non-binary characters as games are an important medium to reproduce or break stereotypes: “it is an important medium of the 21st century. We try to tell stories through the narrative and emphasise other characters, like for example focusing on female characters” (SME member).

There are also networks among female developers, e.g. “virtual women” in Germany, as a female Virtual Reality (VR) professional told us. Especially for her as a working mother, it is difficult to combine the tech industry with her motherhood as the industry moves very fast.

“We do work at a disadvantage a lot of times because we are taking the responsibility of our children, and most of the time we are forced to either sacrifice our career (...) or the time with our kids, right? I mean, it’s a gigantic time investment.”

Apart from the gender gap, there is a clear underrepresentation of people of colour and especially women of colour, as well as differences between Global North and Global South. There are professionals in the global south who created the hardware for example, and there are young women of colour who mostly work in precarious companies. These actors also get excluded from discussions about diversity in the games sector. Another interview partner observed a tendency towards more diversity, but doubted that international major games companies address diversity topics often.

Gender inequalities in the music sector are highlighted in the literature (eg. de Boise, 2019) particularly in genres like jazz (Attrep, 2018; Björck and Bergman, 2018). However, and in contrast to the games sector, findings from the music sector do not reflect in an explicit way much of the struggles as part of an underrepresented group. This is attributed to the gender of the interviewees themselves, as most of them were men. In the Swedish network for example, there were nearly no women. Two interviews of the total 13 were female - the artist and an employee at the larger external record label. In the network from Poland the majority of interviewees, from the artists (male trio) to managers, heads of departments in large companies, and the owner/president of the record label, were men. This parallels the games sector, indicating potential causes such as a lack of role models, discrimination, stereotypes, and prevailing economic trends where men often hold higher positions. In the case of the Polish jazz Trio, gender inequalities extend to the broader labour market, where women face inferior positions, influenced by gender stereotypes and societal expectations, notably in Poland (Kocot-Górecka, Kurowska, 2013). Addressing this entails challenging stereotypes and implementing family-friendly policies to support women’s professional development, including post-childbirth return-to-work initiatives. Educational interventions at the secondary and tertiary levels are also needed to encourage girls in jazz music.

4.4. Working conditions

The music sector findings reveal that the difficulty of breaking into the sector is not limited to the artists in the creative phase but occurs throughout the network. Actors in the production and distribution phase also described their difficulties entering into the sector, working gruelling hours to build contacts and networks, and over time building relationships with the gatekeepers. A concert booker described long hours with little pay, how the passion for the work kept her going and that she was “used to living under the poverty line”. Getting into a position where one is an established actor

“is the fruit of some type of endurance I’d say – you are in a world that if you do things well enough, the people you work with will talk about it. I’d never get a job through putting out an advert somewhere [...]. Everything is very centered around what you do, what comes out of your work, and which reputation you get” (PR agent).

Gaining a reputation, working with people that have a good reputation is key for new actors across the phases to enter into the sector. Some described how they had first worked hard to get into a position at one of the majors, but then left when they had established a network and reputation of their own. This focus on reputation could sometimes be considered hampering the development of their business, and one smaller actor described how

“the largest limit that has been in the company is that even if I perhaps can only work for 10 hours a day, plus concerts at night, I too have perhaps a girlfriend and friends [...]. I think many of my artists don’t see it as that they are working with a company with three employees; they see it as that

they are working with me. It is flattering, but perhaps not always for the best' (live manager).

Power in the music sector is built through trust, reputation and long-term relationships, leaving newer actors with little leverage. Findings from our Sweden network highlight how trust and relationships work as a type of power through the ability to access actors with whom there is mutual trust. Power inequalities in this case were not identified between phases, but with gatekeepers at every phase, creating inequalities between new and established actors. Having access to an actor with an established reputation meant the artist and producer had the ability to choose who to partner with. By already having access to the ecosystem of independent actors in Stockholm, they had, in turn, access to the circle of actors with well-established reputations. Not having access to these types of power translates to inequalities in terms of precarious labour conditions and difficulty for new actors to get compensation, until they can establish a reputation- or opt out of the sector.

The music sector findings do not always confirm precariousness, depending on the artist's position and reputation in the market. For example, the Polish trio members as self-employed negotiate fair earnings due to their experience and reputation. The band manager, also self-employed, avoids precariousness through collaborations with renowned artists. Other interviewees, mainly employed in private or public organisations, work under employment contracts. They acknowledge occasional weekend or night duties and accept it as inherent to the field. In public cultural institutions, low salaries and uncompensated additional work create a disproportionate workload to remuneration.

In the games sector, actors in different GPN phases often endure long working hours, especially at the end of a project. There is a high degree of self-entrepreneurship among professionals. People working in the games sector are highly trained and skilled but salaries do not always correlate with the level of education, skills and knowledge of professionals compared to other sectors, which is why a higher fluctuation of staff is often observed. In addition, professionals are often expected to work internationally, travel and move to other cities, which can be a challenge for private life. The SME we interviewed tries to attract professionals by offering better working conditions and more creative freedom than other bigger international firms, whereas the major firm placed outside of Europe did not address precariousness.

5. Conclusions

By using a GPN approach we were able to locate and discuss inequalities in the music and gaming sectors in a more detailed and causal way. Most importantly, we were able to look into the mechanisms that create inequalities in different phases of the production networks. The GPN approach enabled us to highlight market access disparities, gender and intersectionality inequalities, and critical issues regarding working conditions in the music and games sectors, offering us a more nuanced understanding of the challenges these sectors are facing today.

Potential measures to address such inequalities may be the support and nurturing of versatile ecosystems with smaller and bigger actors, making digital platforms fairly remunerating the artists, ensuring visibility for local actors, or grants for young professionals for activities and networking opportunities in the distribution phases. Increasing public spending on culture and promoting anti-discrimination legislation, as well as measures to combat the glass ceiling phenomenon should also be prioritised. With regards to precarious work in the CCS, policy makers have yet to find a solution. Artistic activities' intermittent nature facilitates a gig economy, while a lack of regulations on artist's status, and especially social security coverage, persists.

Addressing inequalities is paramount in order to improve accessibility, participation and working conditions in the CCS. However, much policy intervention in the CCS is directed at the creation phase and to a lesser extent at the other phases (Kloosterman, 2023). Tackling inequalities in one phase of the network, therefore, does not fight

inequalities in the sector altogether, so taking the entire production network in mind and understanding the mechanisms that create these inequalities is crucial. The GPN approach can be a very useful tool that provides an overview of the complexities of the production network (Vriesema et al., 2024; KEA 2022). In this sense, it can provide the means to consider how inequalities can be addressed, in which phases, through which initiatives and regulations, and as such it could enable the development of appropriate and effective policies and measures to improve many shortcomings in the CCS.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

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There is no competing interest.

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